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EFFECT OF SINTERING TEMPERATURE ON THE CATION DISTRIBUTION OF SOL-GEL PREPARED NiFe₂O₄ NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract:

This work reports the structural characterization of NiFe₂O₄ ferrite nanoparticle sample, prepared by sol-gel auto-combustion process. Prepared samples were sintered at three different temperatures such as 600 °C, 800 °C and 1000 °C for 4 h. X-ray diffraction patterns were used to determine the lattice constant, crystallite size, bulk density and porosity of the prepared samples. It has been observed that the crystallite size increased from 27 nm to 52 nm with the increase in sintering temperature. Bertaut method was applied on the XRD data to estimate the cation distribution of NiFe₂O₄ prepared at different sintering temperatures. It has been observed that Ni²⁺ ions prefer to occupy the octahedral B-site and its occupancy towards octahedral site increased with the increase in sintering temperature. On the other hand Fe³⁺ ions distributed randomly over tetrahedral A- and octahedral B-sites. Theoretical lattice constant and oxygen positional parameter were also calculated from the cation distribution.

Keywords: Nickel ferrite; Sol-gel synthesis; Sintering temperature, Cation distribution

1. Introduction

Ferrite nanoparticles hold a great promise for advanced applications in various technological fields. The application of these materials requires fine control over the nanoparticle size as well as their size distribution [1]. Magnetic properties of ferrite nanoparticles have been intensively studied, and the mechanism of the size effect is generally well understood in terms of the magnetically inactive surface layer [2,3]. The general chemical formula for the spinel-type materials is AB₂O₄. The spinel structure consists of a face-centered cubic lattice of oxygen ions with two types of interstitial holes for cations of tetrahedral (A) and octahedral (B) site symmetries. Cation site preferences in many spinel ferrite are reported [4,5] and some studies [6-8] have given new light in understanding the cation distribution of complex systems. The investigation of cation distribution in spinels,

between tetrahedral and octahedral sites, provides useful information regarding the various factors that determine the coordination preferences. The distribution of cations in a simple end-member oxide spinel may be written $(A_{(1-x)}B_x)^{tet}[A_xB_{(2-x)}]^{oct}O_4$, where x is the inversion parameter. If x is 0, the cations are completely ordered onto the two cation sites, the structural formula is $(A)^{tet}[B_2]^{oct}O_4$, and the spinel is said to have the “normal” cation distribution. The opposite extreme occurs if x is 1, corresponding to $(B)^{tet}[AB]^{oct}O_4$, in which case the spinel is said to have the “inverse” cation arrangement. With increasing temperature there will be a tendency for both normal and inverse spinels to disorder towards the random, maximum entropy, cation arrangement, at $x = 2/3$. Spinel that trend towards $x = 2/3$ from the low x side of this divide are known as “largely normal”, while those whose cation distribution is $x > 2/3$ are “largely inverse” [9]. Nickel ferrite is an inverse spinel in which the tetrahedral (A) site is occupied by Fe^{2+} ions and the octahedral [B] site by Fe^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ion. Recently we have focused our study on nickel and nickel substituted ferrites, due to their potential applications in variety of fields [10,11]. Nickel ferrite is one of the most important magnetic materials and therefore extensively used in high frequency application via microwave devices due to their high resistivity and low losses. In the present work $NiFe_2O_4$ ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel method followed by sintering at 600 °C, 800 °C and 1000 °C for 4h. The main objective of the present study is to study the structural properties and to estimate the cation distribution of $NiFe_2O_4$ with varying sintering temperature.

2. Experimental procedure

Samples of $NiFe_2O_4$ were synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion method using the nitrates of Ni and Fe ions. Reaction procedure was carried out in air atmosphere without the protection of inert gases. The molar ratio of metal nitrates to citric acid was taken as 1:3. The decomposition reaction would not stop before the whole citrate complex was consumed. The auto-ignition was completed within a minute, yielding the brown-colored ashes termed as a precursor. The as-prepared powders of all the samples were sintered at three different temperatures ranging from 600 to 1000 °C. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were recorded by using $Cu-K\alpha$ radiation on Philips X-ray diffractometer (Model PW3710) at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 X-ray Diffraction

The XRD patterns of NiFe₂O₄ were recorded at room temperature. The typical X-ray diffraction patterns for samples sintered at 600 °C, 800 °C and 1000 °C are shown in Fig. 1. The XRD patterns indicate that as sintering temperature increases the broadening of the diffraction lines decreases. The broadening is attributed to particle size effect. The analysis of XRD patterns shows that the sample possesses single phase cubic spinel structure.

Fig. 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of NiFe₂O₄ sintered at 600 °C, 800 °C and 1000 °C

The XRD patterns were used to determine crystallite size, lattice constant, X-ray density and cation distribution. The lattice parameter ‘*a*’ was calculated using the following equation [12];

$$a = d\sqrt{(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)} \quad (1)$$

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where d is the inter-planer spacing and (hkl) is the index of the XRD reflection peak. The values of lattice constant were obtained from XRD data and are presented in Fig. 2. It is observed from Fig. 2 that the lattice constant increases as sintering temperature increases.

The average crystallite size (t) was determined by means of line broadening of most intense (311) diffraction peak using Debye Scherrer formula [12],

$$t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B \cos\theta} \quad (2)$$

where λ is the wavelength, B is full width at half maximum intensity in radian, θ is Bragg angle.

Fig. 2: Variation of lattice constant with sintering temperature.

Fig. 3: Variation of crystallite size with sintering temperature.

Variation of crystallite size determined at three different sintering temperature are shown in Fig. 3. It is evident from Fig. 3 that the crystallite size was found to increase with the increase in sintering temperature. While sintering generally decreases the lattice defects and strains, however it can also cause coalescence of crystallites that result in increasing the average size of the nanoparticles [13]. Values of bulk densities and porosities at different sintering temperature were calculated and are their variation is presented in Fig. 4. The higher sintering temperature synthesis causes the particle size to increase and removes the pore contents, which lead to densification of the samples. Porosity of corresponding materials was also calculated. The higher annealing temperature removes more pore contents. Hence, porosity of the samples decreases as increasing annealing temperature

Fig. 4: Variation of bulk density and porosity with sintering temperature.

3.2 Cation distribution

In spinel ferrite cations are located at two sites namely tetrahedral (A) and octahedral [B] sites. The distribution of cations at tetrahedral (A) and octahedral [B] sites is known as cation distribution. The cation distribution depends on various parameters like method of preparation, preparative parameter (sintering temperature, sintering atmosphere, cooling rate etc.) and the type and amount of dopant. The distribution of cations in A and B sites influences the properties of ferrite. The cation distribution can be estimated from the X-ray diffraction [14], Mössbauer analysis [15], and neutron diffraction [16]. In the present work, cation distribution of NiFe₂O₄ was determined by X-ray diffraction method. The cation distribution in spinel ferrites can be obtained from the X-ray intensity ratio calculations. The Bertaut [17] and Furuhashi et al. [18] obtained cation distribution in spinel ferrite based on a comparison between diffraction intensities observed experimentally and those calculated for a large number of hypothetical crystal structures. The best information on cation distribution is achieved by comparing experimental and calculated intensity ratios for reflections whose intensities; (1) was nearly independent of the oxygen parameter, (2) vary with the cation distribution in opposite way and does not differ significantly. The intensity of the reflection due to the plane (hkl) is given by the following relation

$$I_{hkl} = [F_{hkl}] P \left[\frac{1 + \cos^2 2\theta}{\sin^2 \theta \cdot \cos \theta} \right] \quad (3)$$

where I_{hkl} is the Intensity of plane (hkl), P is Multiplicity factor for the plane (hkl), $(1 + \cos^2 2\theta) / (\sin^2 \theta \cos \theta)$ is Lorentz polarization factor. In calculating intensity of (hkl) planes temperature and absorption factors are not taken in to account in our calculations as these factors do not affect intensity ratio calculation [19]. The planes (220), (400), (440) are considered for intensity calculations as these planes are most suitable for intensity calculations. The values of multiplicity factor ‘P’ and Lorentz polarization factor ‘L_P’ are taken from literature [20]. The calculated intensities were compared with observed intensity ratios. The X-ray intensity ratio calculations were carried out for several distributions of Ni²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions at tetrahedral (A) and octahedral [B]. The cation distribution is finalized where observed and calculated intensity ratios were agreed close to each other. The cation distribution obtained in this manner is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Cation distribution of NiFe₂O₄ estimated from Bertaut method

Sintering temperature	Tetrahedral A-site	Octahedral B-site
600 °C	Ni _{0.3} Fe _{0.7}	Ni _{0.7} Fe _{1.3}
800 °C	Ni _{0.2} Fe _{0.8}	Ni _{0.8} Fe _{1.2}
1000 °C	Ni _{0.05} Fe _{0.95}	Ni _{0.95} Fe _{1.05}

It has been observed that Ni²⁺ ions preferably occupy octahedral B site for the sample sintered at 600 °C. As the sintering temperature increased from 600 to 1000 °C, the occupancy of Ni ions at octahedral site increased. This is an indication that NiFe₂O₄ posses inverse spinel structure at higher sintering temperature. The theoretical values of lattice parameter can be calculated with the help of following equation [21],

$$a_{th} = \frac{8}{3} \sqrt{3} [(r_A + R_0) + \sqrt{3}(r_B + R_0)] \quad (4)$$

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where r_A and r_B are radii of tetrahedral (A) site and octahedral [B] site, R_O is radius of oxygen i.e. ($R_O = 1.32 \text{ \AA}$). The variation of theoretical values as shown in Fig. 5 is similar to that observed for experimentally determined lattice parameter. Using the values of 'a', the radius of oxygen ion $R_O = 1.32 \text{ \AA}$ and ' r_A ' in the following expression, the oxygen positional parameter ' u ' can be calculated [22],

$$u = \left[(r_A + R_O) \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}a} + \frac{1}{4} \right] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 5 shows that oxygen positional parameter decreased slightly from 0.3872-0.3869 Å. In most oxide spinels the oxygen ions are apparently larger than the metallic ions. In spinel like structure the oxygen positional parameter has a value in the neighborhood of 0.375 Å for which the arrangement of O^{2-} ions are equals exactly a cubic closed packing but in actual spinel lattice, this ideal pattern is slightly deformed. In the present work $u > 0.375$ may be due to anion displacement from the ideal situation so that it forms expanded tetrahedral interstices. The lattice disturbance is confirmed from the data for lattice constant and the oxygen positional parameter ' u '.

Fig. 5: Variation of theoretical lattice constant and oxygen parameter with sintering temperature.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of XRD patterns confirms that all the samples possess single phase cubic spinel structure. Lattice constant (a) is increased with the increase in sintering temperature. The size of the nanoparticles increased linearly with the increase in sintering temperature, which is due to the coalescence that increases as annealing temperature increases. The cation distribution data suggest that Ni²⁺ occupies tetrahedral (A) site and Fe³⁺ occupy octahedral [B] site. Theoretical lattice constant almost remain constant whereas oxygen parameter decreased with the increase in sintering temperature.

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